

INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SERVICE MARKETS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION

Abdullayeva Zamira Muhtarovna

Doctoral student of the Samarkand State University
named after Sharaf Rashidov

Abstract. The conducted study in this article consist of the problems of innovative development of higher education service markets in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the conditions of digitalization of the modern economy. The most important purpose of the study is to study the directions and methods of improving the higher education service system of the republic as an important factor in the intensification of production and, above all, a key condition for strengthening the intensive nature of the economy, which in modern conditions is the process of digitalization. In addition, other research objectives are also highlighted, in particular, the work examines and highlights the activities implemented by the country's leadership and aimed at the development of the digital economy, which also determine the ways of innovative development of the state's higher education system.

Keywords: innovative development, digitalization of society, economy, higher education services.

At present, the Republic of Uzbekistan is trying to implement the most effective mechanisms for the functioning of the higher education system in the context of the digitalisation of the economy, while taking into account the need for effective implementation of the country's socio-economic policy. In recent years, the main problem of education in Uzbekistan has been to improve its quality and increase its role in the process of modernising society. Thus, the growth of the quality of education in the country should be a determining condition for the effective development of society. As can be seen, the study of innovative development of

higher education appears to be very relevant. Over the years of independence, Uzbekistan’s higher education system has undergone major changes connected with improving the quality of education and its adaptability and flexibility to the innovative conditions of economic development. This is due to the fact that there has been:

- The legal and regulatory framework for higher education has been established;
- Multi-level structure of higher education (bachelor — master — post-graduate — doctorate) was introduced;
- Correspondence and evening classes have been introduced;

- Conditions have been created for the opening and operation of foreign and non-governmental higher education institutions, etc.

However, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan S. Mirziyoyev UP 5847 of 08.10.2023 [1] states that there are still a number of pressing problems in the field of higher education with regard to the process of training highly qualified personnel that require immediate solutions. In addition, it is clear to everyone that the growing needs of society have turned modernisation and innovative development into the main means of survival and overcoming negative factors and trends in market conditions.

The “Concept of Development of Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” [2] identifies some directions for the introduction of progressive models and standards of education, such as phased transition to higher education system aimed at building skills and approaches to the effective implementation of economic processes, including the phased implementation of the concept of “University 3.0”. It is obvious that the improvement of the education sector is the most important condition for the intensive development of the socio-economic system and for increasing its efficiency.

The importance of ongoing processes of digitalization as one of the most important directions of intensification of social reproduction has allowed to raise the question of formation and development of a new type of economy, where the

dominant importance is acquired by relations concerning the improvement of education. In accordance with the adopted strategy “Digital Uzbekistan — 2030”, it is necessary to maintain macroeconomic stability and ensure a leap in economic development of the republic and achieve advanced positions in the ranking of competitiveness of world economies [3]. However, under these conditions, it is necessary to accelerate the scientific and technological development of the country, in particular, it is necessary to implement the introduction of digital technologies in all areas of activity, as well as investment in human capital and, especially, in education, from early childhood to adulthood, which contributes to a significant return on the economy and society.

The Statement of the President of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev to Oliy Majlis from 30.12.2022 marks, that really without modern knowledge it is impossible to develop any region, any branch. This is evidenced by the fact that in developed countries more than 50% of gross domestic product is created by the “knowledge economy”, i.e. innovation and highly qualified personnel [4]. In another of his speeches, the President notes that in Uzbekistan, “in competition, those firms, countries and regions of the world that create and master new knowledge faster and more effectively than others, better adapt the products and services offered to the differentiated and dynamically evolving needs of people win. Vocational education will be reformed based on new approaches in accordance with labour market requirements and international standards” [5]. The core of the digital economy is the sector for the production of digital goods and the provision of digital services as the basis for digital education. It is estimated that the digital economy will allow for an increase in Uzbekistan’s gross domestic product of at least 30% and a drastic reduction in corruption, while savings of 25- 30% can be achieved by monitoring and managing electricity grids using information and communication technologies. Given the importance of the process of digitalisation of the economy, it makes sense to take a closer look at the essence, methods and forms of its current implementation. To ensure the sustainable development of society, its digitalization at different hierarchical levels of the management system is the most important condition, along

with such factors and conditions as ensuring security, satisfying material needs, forming effective social relations, reducing poverty, reducing income differentiation and other factors and conditions. Obviously, this can only be done over a sufficiently long period of time. In order to achieve the goal of sustainable societal development it is necessary to implement strategies and policies that balance the different ingredients of society such as economic growth, social development and ecological balance. At the same time, it is clear that a decisive role in the process of achieving sustainable societal development through the formation of a long-term balance between societal development and the natural environment is played by modern technology, with a particular emphasis recently placed on the material and technical basis of digitalisation — ICT (information and communication technology), which emerged in relation to this kind of technology in the late 1990s and early years of this century.

However, as a phenomenon of modernity, the process of digitalisation dates back to the late forties of the twentieth century, i.e. with the emergence of the first computers and, accordingly, the essence of this process is the digital representation of data in its storage, transmission and processing [6]. Since that time, the potential

and importance of ICT for the development of the digital economy has been fully revealed. At present, the sustainability of the functioning of society in the context of digitalization depends on the effective and interconnected operation of all elements of the management hierarchy of the entire society. As a result, the current state of affairs in the digital economy is characterized not only by the fact that ICTs are spreading in many spheres of society, but also by the fact that there is a change in the system of social trust, development of social contacts, strengthening of individualization tendencies, which significantly affects the dynamics of reproduction structures and elements (production, distribution, exchange, consumption, interpersonal property relations, etc.).

At present, the Republic of Uzbekistan employs about 29,000 people in the ICT sector, working at 1,400 enterprises, whose total contribution to GDP is 2.2%. Today in the labour market, IT specialists account for about 1% of the total employed

population of the country, and by 2025 it is planned to increase this figure to 2.5-3%, which corresponds to the global average level. The number of internet users increased by 1.2 million in 2020 compared to 2018, the number of social network users in the country increased by 44% in the same period, and the number of mobile connections increased by 76%. The total volume of communication and informatization services (wireline and mobile services, Internet network, satellite communication services, etc.) of Uzbekistan in 2020 is 12101 billion soums, which is 8.9% more than in the previous year.[7] In general, the following list of effective measures implemented by states and aimed at developing the digital economy can be highlighted, which, in our opinion, should include the following:

- Building scientific and social networks;
- Development of productive and social infrastructure and its various elements;
- Characterizing all kinds of barriers in the system of digital economy facilities;
- Ensuring the security of the digital infrastructure;
- Assessment of the various risks associated with the digitalisation process;
- Training and retraining of specialists in the field of digitalisation;
- Development of education related to information security;
- Investment and innovation in the information sector of the economy [8].

In Uzbekistan, as in many other countries, the issues of doing business in the field of crypto assets and currencies are increasingly beginning to be considered, including the creation of infrastructure for the circulation of cryptocurrency assets (e.g. crypto exchanges for trading crypto assets), legal regulation and the necessary legal environment for the introduction of digital technologies.

Overall, such issues are also related to the challenges of digitalisation of society. As in many countries, the government of Uzbekistan has recently taken a wide range of measures to further develop the digitalisation process, including in education, the increasing introduction of electronic payment and electronic document management systems, and the improvement of the legal conditions for the implementation of e-commerce.

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